

ON THE STABILITY OF INNER-METALLIC COMPLEXES

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A detailed study of the mechanism of formation and dissociation of a series of copper and nickel biguanide complexes has been made in aqueous solution. The variations of the acid-dissociation constants of the ligand with substitution against the change in the stability of the respective complexes have been discussed. The results are compatible with a single-step dissociation for the Ni bis-biguanides and Cu and Ni dibiguanides as compared to the distinct two-step-dissociation of the Cu bis-biguanide complexes.

A detailed study of the mechanism of formation and stability of co-ordination complexes was initiated mainly by N. Bjerrum and his school with the observation that the formation of complex ions always occurred stepwise. The problem of complex formation has been treated on a statistical basis by J. Bjerrum ("Metal ammine formation in aqueous solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941), involving all the possible intermediate stages in a reversible manner.

Bjerrum's method has been successfully employed to the case of inner-metallic complexes by Calvin and Wilson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1334), Mellor *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 401), Ackerman *et al.* (*Nature*, 1949, 163, 723) and others.

Inner-metallic complexes of higher order, formed by biguanidine molecules as ligands with metal ions like Cu, Ni, Co, Ag and Pd, have been the subject matter of investigation by P. Rây and co-workers in this laboratory for the last few years. These form very convenient starting materials for a quantitative survey of the nature and stability of inner-metallic complexes in as much as the ligands and the complex chlorides, formed by them, are, as a rule, freely soluble in water and are easily obtainable in the pure solid state. A study of the mechanism of decomposition of these complexes and of their relative stabilities constitute the purpose of the present investigation.

The biguanide complex of bivalent metals reacts with acids in aqueous solution in the following way :

where M is a bivalent metal ion like Cu^{2+} or Ni^{2+} and BigH and BigH_2^+ represent respectively the biguanide base and biguanidinium ion corresponding to the uptake of a proton.

The equilibrium constants of the reactions (1) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} k'_2 &= \frac{[M(\text{BigH})]^{2+} [\text{BigH}_2]^+}{[M(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+} [\text{H}^+]} \\ k'_1 &= \frac{[M]^{2+} [\text{BigH}_2]^+}{[M(\text{BigH})]^{2+} [\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots \quad \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

These are related to the successive instability or dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 , in the following way :

$$k_2 = \frac{[M(\text{BigH})]^{2+}}{[M(\text{BigH}_2)]^{2+}} \cdot [\text{BigH}] = \frac{[M(\text{BigH})]^{2+}}{[M(\text{BigH}_2)]^{2+}} \cdot \frac{[\text{BigH}_2]^+}{[\text{H}^+]} \cdot \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{BigH}]}{[\text{BigH}_2]^+} \\ = k'_2 \cdot k_1^* ; \text{ similarly } k_1 = k'_1 \cdot k_1^* \quad \dots (3)$$

where k_1^* is the first acid-dissociation constant of the co-ordinated ligand, from $\text{BigH}_2^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{BigH} + \text{H}^+$.

The determination of the acid-dissociation constants of the biguanide bases has been described in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 217).

The experimental technique employed for the determination of k'_1 and k'_2 was simpler and was more straight forward than those adopted by earlier workers. Evaluation of k'_1 and k'_2 was made from a measurement of the p_H values of the equilibrium mixture of a known amount of the complex and definite volumes of standard acid of widely varying strengths at a constant temperature.

The complex salts employed were the hydrochlorides, due to their reasonably high solubility, and the acid used was hydrochloric acid.

Formation of any chloro-complex of copper and nickel in appreciable amounts may be neglected in the light of the works of Carlson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1334) and also of Sockelberg and Freyhold (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1940, 46, 120).

The calculation is made as follows :

Let X = total concentration of non-complex-bound biguanide liberated at equilibrium. Then

$$X = \text{BigH} + \text{BigH}_2^+ + \text{BigH}_3^{3+} \\ = \text{BigH}_2^+ \left(\frac{k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} + 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} \right) \\ = \text{BigH}_2^+ \left(\frac{k_1^* k_2^* + k_2^* [\text{H}^+] + [\text{H}^+]^2}{k_2^* [\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots (4)$$

Let Z = acid consumed in the process at equilibrium by the reaction of the added acid with the complex, obtained from the initial p_H of the acid and the final p_H values of the solution mixture and the p_H -acid relation graph. Then

$$Z = C_H - C'_H$$

(where C_H and C'_H represent respectively concentration of the total acid added and of that present at equilibrium derived from the observed p_H and the acid- p_H relation)

$$= \text{BigH}_2^+ + 2 \text{BigH}_3^{3+} \\ = \text{BigH}_2^+ \left(1 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots (5)$$

(acid liberated by the reaction $\text{BigH} = \text{Big}^- + \text{H}^+$ being negligible in solution of $p_H < 9$).

From (4) and (5)

$$\text{BigH}_2^+ = \frac{Z \cdot k_2^*}{k_2^* + 2 [\text{H}^+]} \quad \text{and} \\ X = \frac{Z \cdot (k_1^* \cdot k_2^* + k_2^* [\text{H}^+] + [\text{H}^+]^2)}{k_2^* [\text{H}^+] + 2 [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad \dots (6)$$

Let the concentration of the complex taken = C and at equilibrium

$$\begin{aligned} [M(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+} &= C_2 \\ [M(\text{BigH})]^{2+} &= C_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$[M^{2+}] = C_0 \text{ and } \frac{[\text{BigH}_2]^+}{[H^+]} = [b]$$

Then $C = C_2 + C_1 + C_0$... (7)

When $X < C$, C_0 is negligible or $C = C_2 + C_1$;

$$C_1 = X \text{ and } C_2 = C - X$$

giving from (2), $k'_2 = \frac{X}{C - X} \cdot b$... (8)

Again, when $X > C$, but $< 2C$, C_2 is negligible, and $C = C_1 + C_0$, $C_1 = 2C - X$ and $C_0 = X - C$, whence,

$$k'_1 = \frac{X - C}{2C - X} \cdot [b] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The relation between $\bar{n}$ and $\log ([\text{BigH}_2^+]/[H^+]) = \log [b]$ may be plotted in a graph, where $\bar{n}$ = average number of biguanide molecules attached to a metal ion. Then

$$\bar{n} = \frac{C_1 + 2C_2}{C_0 + C_1 + C_2} = \frac{2C - X}{C} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

substituting for C_1 , C_2 etc. from (8) and (9)

$$\bar{n} = \frac{k'_2 \cdot [b] + 2[b]^2}{k'_1 \cdot k'_2 + k'_2 \cdot b + [b]^2} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

which can be written as

$$k'_1 = [b] \frac{1 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n}} + \frac{2 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n}} \cdot [b]^2 \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

Again, when $\bar{n} = n - \frac{1}{2}$, the concentration of MA_n and MA_{n-1} becomes practically equal and $k'_n = [b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}}'$ to a first approximation from equation (12)

$$k'_1 = [b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left(2 + \frac{3}{k_2} \cdot [b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

and

$$k'_2 = [b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}}' \cdot \left(\frac{[b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}}}{3k'_1 + [b]_{n-\frac{1}{2}}} \right)$$

From which the values of k'_1 and k'_2 may be accurately obtained, whence equation (3) gives the successive instability constants.

The stability of a few of these complexes was also determined from a study of their formation from metal ions and the biguanide salt solutions, which give rise to the complexes $M(\text{BigH})^{2+}$ and $M(\text{BigH})_2^{2+}$, depending upon the p_H of the mixture. Thus,

$$\text{whence, } k'_{11} = \frac{C_1}{C_0} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} = \frac{I}{k'_1} \text{ and}$$

$$k'_{12} = \frac{C_2}{C_1} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} = \frac{I}{k'_2}$$

where k'_{11} and k'_{12} are related to the formation constants of the system and C_0 , C_1 , C_2 and $[b]$ have their usual significance.

Let C_A = total biguanide added, A_c = biguanide in complex and A_n = not complex-bound biguanide

C_M = total metal concentration.

Z = acid liberated in the reaction.

C'_M = acid concentration in the final mixture.

C_M = acid concentration of the component solutions before mixing.

C_M' = acid equivalent of the alkali added.

Now $Z = C_M' - C_M + C'_M$ and

$$C_A = A_c + A_n = A_c + \text{BigH}_3^{2+} + \text{BigH}_2^+ + \text{BigH}$$

$$A_c = A_c + \text{BigH}_2^+ \cdot \left(\frac{H^+}{k_2^*} + 1 + \frac{k_1^*}{H^+} \right) \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

and $Z = A_c + \text{BigH} + \text{BigH}_3^{2+}$

$$\text{From (14) and (15), } A_c = A_c + \text{BigH}_2^+ \cdot \left(\frac{k_1^*}{H^+} - \frac{H^+}{k_2^*} \right) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

From (14) and (15),

$$\text{BigH}_2^+ = \frac{(C_A - Z) k_1^*}{k_2^* - 2H^+} \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

$$\text{And } A_c = Z - \frac{(C_A - Z) (k_1^* k_2^* - [H^+]^2)}{H^+ k_2^* + 2[H^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

when $A_c \ll C_M$, C_2 is negligibly small.

$$C_M = C_0 + C_1 \\ A_c = C_1; C_0 = C_M - A_c$$

$$\text{giving } k'_{11} = \frac{C_1}{C_0} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} = \frac{A_c}{C_M - A_c} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

Again when $A_c > C_M$, but $< 2 C_M$, C_0 is negligibly small, Hence

$$C_M = C_1 + C_2 \text{ and } A_c = C_1 + 2C_2 \\ C_2 = A_c - C_M; C_1 = 2C_M - A_c$$

$$\text{giving } k'_{12} = \frac{C_2}{C_1} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} = \frac{A_c - C_M}{2C_M - A_c} \cdot \frac{I}{[b]} \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

The decomposition mechanism of dibiguanide complexes can be satisfactorily represented by a single-step process found from the present physico-chemical study in the following form:

where M is a bivalent metal ion like Cu^{2+} or Ni^{2+} , and A represents a molecule of a dibiguanide base, while AH_2^{2+} is the dibiguanidinium ion corresponding to the uptake of two protons.

The equilibrium constant of (20) is given by

$$K' = \frac{M^{2+} \cdot AH_2^{2+}}{MA^{2+} \cdot [H^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

As before, if X and Z represent the total biguanide liberated and the acid consumed in the process at equilibrium respectively,

$$X = AH_2^{2+} \left[\frac{k_1^* k_2^*}{[H^+]^2} + \frac{k_2^*}{[H^+]} + 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_3^*} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_3^* k_4^*} \right] \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

where k_1^* , k_2^* , k_3^* and k_4^* are the successive acid-dissociation constants of the dibiguanide.

$$= AH_2^{2+} \left[\frac{k_2^*}{[H^+]} + 2 + 3 \cdot \frac{[H^+]}{k_3^*} + 4 \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_3^* k_4^*} \right] \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

From (22) and (23),

$$[AH_2^{2+}]^{2+} = \frac{Z \cdot [H^+] \cdot k_3^* k_4^*}{k_2^* k_3^* k_4^* + 2[H^+] \cdot k_3^* k_4^* + 3[H^+]^2 \cdot k_3^* + 4[H^+]^3}$$

$X =$

$$\frac{Z}{[H^+]} \cdot \frac{k_1^* k_2^* k_3^* k_4^* + [H^+] k_2^* k_3^* k_4^* + [H^+]^2 k_3^* k_4^* + [H^+]^3 k_4^* + [H^+]^4}{k_2^* k_3^* k_4^* + 2[H^+] \cdot k_3^* k_4^* + 3[H^+]^2 \cdot k_3^* + 4[H^+]^3} \quad (24)$$

Let C = concentration of total complex taken,

C_0 = metal ion in solution at equilibrium = M^{2+} and

C_2 = concentration of complex ion in solution at equilibrium. Then

$$C = C_2 + C_0$$

$$X = M^{2+} = C_0 \text{ and } C - X = C_2, \text{ giving}$$

$$K' = \frac{[M^{2+}]}{[MA]^{2+}} \cdot \frac{[AH_2^{2+}]}{[H^+]^2} = \frac{C_0}{C_2} \cdot [b] = \frac{X}{C - X} \cdot [b] \quad \dots \quad (25)$$

where $[b] = [AH_2^{2+}]/[H^+]^2$.

As usual the decomposition curve is obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ and $\log [b]$ where

$\bar{n}$ = average number of ligands attached per metal ion,

$$= \frac{\text{complex-bound ligand}}{\text{total metal conc.}} = \frac{C - X}{C} \quad \dots \quad (26)$$

Again, from (5),

$$\bar{n} = \frac{[MA]^{2+}}{[M]^{2+} + [MA]^{2+}} = \frac{[M]^{2+} \cdot [b]/K'}{[M]^{2+} + [M]^{2+} \cdot [b]/K'} = \frac{[b]}{K' + [b]} \quad (27)$$

or

$$K' = (1 - \bar{n}/\bar{n}) \cdot [b] \quad \text{i.e. } K' = [b]_{\bar{n}=1/2} \quad \dots \quad (28)$$

The instability constant K is then obtained from the equilibrium constant K' , using the expression

$$K = K' \cdot k_1^* \cdot k_2^* \quad \dots \quad (29)$$

where k_1^* and k_2^* are the first two acid-dissociation constants of the ligand.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method of preparation of the N-alkyl biguanide complexes is essentially similar, viz., heating under pressure a mixture of copper sulphate, dicyandiamide and the corresponding amine in aqueous solution. The resulting solution on cooling yields the complex sulphate, which forms the starting material for the preparation of the biguanide and its complex copper and nickel chlorides.

TABLE I

Compound.	References.	Calculated.			Found.		
		% Cu.	% N.	% Cl.	% Cu.	% N.	% Cl.
1. Copper bis-biguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Bagchi, this <i>Journal</i> , 1939, 18, 617	17.07	37.57	19.06	17.10	37.52	19.09
2. Copper bis-methylbiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_9\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Reibenschutt, <i>Monatsch.</i> , 1883, 4, 394.	15.52	34.15	17.43	15.99	34.21	17.49
3. Copper bis-ethylbiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		15.82	34.87	17.59	15.87	34.90	17.63
4. Copper bis-phenylbiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Chakravarty, this <i>Journal</i> , 1941, 18, 609.	12.64	27.64	14.05	12.53	27.65	14.03
5. Copper bis-dimethylbiguanide chloride		14.45	31.85	16.15	14.48	31.99	16.17
6. Copper bis-diethylbiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Ghosh, <i>ibid.</i> , 1949, 26, 144.	13.35	29.44	14.95	13.55	29.50	13.05
7. Copper ethylene-dibiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_{10}) \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Ghosh, <i>ibid.</i> , 1943, 20, 291.	16.43	...	18.30	16.45	...	18.32
8. Copper m-phenylene-dibiguanide chloride $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_{10}) \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Siddhanta, <i>ibid.</i> , 1943, 20, 200.	14.52	32.00	16.23	14.55	32.02	16.22
9. Nickel bis-biguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_5)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Purkayastha, <i>ibid.</i> , 1941, 18, 217.	15.37	38.03	19.40	16.01	38.00	19.46
10. Nickel bis-methylbiguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_9\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		13.31	31.98	16.10	13.35	32.01	16.54
11. Nickel bis-ethylbiguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		14.79	35.29	17.89	14.82	35.32	17.89
12. Nickel bis-phenylbiguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Ray & Chakravarty, <i>loc. cit.</i>	11.10	26.48	13.43	11.14	26.50	13.41
13. Nickel bis-dimethylbiguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		14.09	33.59	17.04	14.08	33.60	17.09
14. Nickel bis-diethylbiguanide chloride $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		12.96	30.92	15.66	12.99	20.98	15.67
15. Nickel ethylene-dibiguanide chloride	Ray & Ghosh, <i>loc. cit.</i> , 1943,	15.31	...	18.50	15.30	...	18.48

TABLE II
Decomposition of copper bis-phenylbiguanide chloride.

C_L	p_a	$\text{BigH}_2^+ \times 10$	$X \cdot 10^3$	n	$\log(\text{BigH}_2^+ / \text{H}^+)$	$k_1 \times 10^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^{-3}$
0.0025	6.09	2.499	2.500	1.750	3.468		1.024
0.0040	5.64	3.995	3.997	1.600	3.242	...	1.166
0.0050	5.38	4.994	4.996	1.500	3.078	...	1.196
0.0060	5.15	5.982	5.987	1.401	2.957	...	1.357
0.0075	4.87	7.457	7.471	1.253	2.743	...	1.637
0.0100	4.38	9.837	9.897	1.010	2.373	...	2.268
0.0125	3.97	12.010	12.200	0.780	2.050	3.162	
0.0150	3.60	13.730	14.220	0.578	1.738	3.989	
0.0175	3.27	14.730	15.820	0.418	1.458	3.989	
0.0200	3.05	15.090	17.030	0.297	1.229	4.007	

$k'_1 = 4.524 \times 10^1$; $k'_2 = 1.076 \times 10^3$ from Fig. 1 (after correction)

Expt. mean of $k'_1 = 3.5189 \times 10^1$.

$k'_2 = 1.436 \times 10^3$.

$K = k_1 \cdot k_2 = k'_1 \cdot k_1^* \cdot k'_2 k_2^* = 1.77 \times 10^{-17}$.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

Formation of copper phenylbiguanide.

$\text{Cu}^{2+} = 0.01M$. p_H of $0.01M$ -phenylbiguanide chloride solution = 5.70.

Temp. = 32° . p_H of $0.01M$ copper chloride solution = 4.71.

BigH ₂ ⁺ added.	KOH added.	p_H .	BigH ₂ ⁺ × 10 ² .	BigH-in complex × 10 ² .	$k'_{11} \times 10^2$.	$k_{12} \times 10^2$.
0.0050		3.15	0.366	1.080	2.043	
0.0100	...	3.14	0.760	1.606	1.742	
0.0150	...	3.12	1.082	2.119	1.884	
0.0200	...	3.11	1.562	2.620	1.765	
0.0250	...	3.11	1.971	3.063	1.740	
0.0175	0.0150	5.83	0.227	14.970	—	6.442
0.0200	0.0150	5.47	0.502	14.970	—	6.679
0.0225	0.0150	5.29	0.736	14.980	—	6.917
0.0250	0.0150	5.02	0.999	14.980	—	9.143

Mean of $k'_{11} = 0.01635$; $k'_{12} = 0.00073$.

giving for $K = 2.58 \times 10^{-17}$.

TABLE IV

	$k_1\text{Cu} \cdot 10^{12}$.	$k_2\text{Cu} \cdot 10^9$.	$K\text{Cu} \cdot 10^{19}$.	$K\text{Ni} \cdot 10^{14}$.	$K\text{Cu} \cdot 10^{19}$.	$K\text{Ni} \cdot 10^{14}$.
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Biguanide	7.87	5.76	4.54	3.31	4.68	2.86
Methyl biguanide	29.85	23.62	70.52	166.00	69.20	168.00
Ethyl biguanide	36.84	27.65	101.90	166.30	105.80	149.20
Phenyl biguanide	85.21	20.50	177.00	524.80	177.30	563.20
Dimethyl biguanide	241.50(319.90)	(85.09)	(2722.00)	(4266.00)	—	...
Diethyl biguanide	(1045.00)	(467.70)	(489700.00)	...	—	...
Ethylene dibiguanide	...	...	0.0022	0.0708	0.0021	0.0786
m-Phenylene dibiguanide	...	...	36310.00	...	31452.00	...
Glycine	660.60	141.30	9333.00	...	9323.00	...

Values in columns (1) to (4) are obtained from Figs. 1-4 after correction; those in (5) and (6) are experimental mean values. Ni-m-phenylene-dibiguanide could not be prepared in a pure state and the stability constants of dialkyl biguanide complexes could not be studied as decomposition reactions due to separation of metal hydroxides are reported from the data of Ray & Das Sarma (*Naturwiss.*, 1955; 42, 415) in parenthesis.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

TABLE V

	pK_1^*	pK_2^*	pK_1^{Cu}	pK_2^{Cu}	$\frac{pK_1^{Cu}}{pK_2^{Cu}}$	pK_{av}^{Cu}	pK_{av}	$\frac{pK_{av}^{Cu}}{pK_1^*}$	$\frac{pK_{av}^{Cu}}{pK_1^*}$
Big ^a	11.52	7.23	10.10	8.24	1.23	8.17	6.74	0.80	0.58
MeBig ^a	11.44	7.22	9.53	7.63	1.25	8.58	5.89	0.75	0.51
Et Big ^a	11.47	6.78	9.43	7.56	1.25	8.51	5.89	0.74	0.51
PhBig ^a	10.72	6.44	9.07	7.69	1.18	8.38	5.64	0.78	0.53
DiMe Big ^a	11.52	7.15	8.50	7.07	1.20	7.79	5.28	0.68	0.46
DiEt Big ^a	11.68	7.11	7.98	6.33	1.26	7.15	...	0.61	...
Ethylene diBig ^a	11.55	6.87 ^d	...	...	...	10.83	7.58	0.94	0.66
<i>m</i> -Phenylene diBig ^a	10.63	6.10 ^d	...	...	...	7.22	...	0.68	...
Glycine ^e	9.55	5.90	8.13	6.85	1.29	7.54	...	0.79	...
Ethylenediamine ^b	9.92	8.60	10.55	9.05	1.06	9.80	6.90	0.99	0.70
Salicylaldehyde ^c	9.50	8.45	7.50	5.80	1.29	6.65	4.56	0.70	0.48

a—present investigation; b—Carlson, McReynolds & Verhoek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1334.

c—Calvin & Wilson, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 2003.

d— $1/2 (pK_1^* + pK_2^*)$ values.

e—Ray & Das Sarma, *Naturwiss.*, 1959, 46, 415. $pK_{av} = 1/n (pK_1 + pK_2 + \dots + pK_n)$.

DISCUSSION

It has already been pointed out in an earlier communication that the biguanide molecule behaves as an ampholyte acting as a potential acid (I) and a diacid base (II).

The ratio, pk^*_1/pk^*_2 , for biguanides is about 4~5, so that, as a base it may be considered to behave as a mono-acid one, to a fair degree of approximation. The average formation or stability constant of the system,

may be compared with

so that, we may expect a rough proportionality between the first acid-dissociation constant and the average stability of the complex formed with the base, arguing after Calvin and co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

This point has been elucidated by Bjerrum (*Chem. Rev.*, 1950, 46, 386) showing that the ratio $\log k_w / \log k_M$ (where $k_w = \Delta H / A.H$ and k_M = the mean complexity constant of the metal) is 0.35-0.40 for Ag, 0.78-0.87 for Hg for ligands with one point of attachment, though values 0.22 for the first and 0.96 have also been recorded for the two groups of systems respectively. Calvin and Wilson (*loc. cit.*) have similarly given a ratio of 0.9 for β -diketones and 0.6-0.7 for salicylaldehyde complexes of copper.

In the present case, more or less concordant values of the ratio $\log k_M/\log k_s$ has been obtained with X_n as the first acid-dissociation constant.

But it can be examined further purely from the point of view of energetics. Hydrogen, as is well known, is incapable of forming two stable covalent bonds, as it can have only one stable orbital. The two cases are therefore not exactly parallel.

It is obvious that there is some optimum basic strengths for ligands. Too strong an acid or too strong a base will tend to form ionic bonds, and hence, will not be suitable for the formation of covalent complexes.

A comparison of the data in Table V at once reveals some interesting points, *i.e.*, the abnormally high values (0.94-0.99 and 0.66-0.7) of $\log k_M/\log k_s$ ratio for ethylene dibiguanide and ethylenediamine as ligands. This deviation from the normal value (0.7-0.8 and 0.51-0.58) may be somehow connected with the occurrence of five-membered rings in the complexes formed. The lower value with *m*-phenylenedibiguanide-Cu system might be attributed to steric factors.

The values for the stability of the copper biguanide complexes lie at about 10^4 to 10^6 times greater than those for the corresponding nickel compounds. It has further been found that while copper complexes suffer stepwise decomposition, affording well defined instability constants k_1^{Cu} and k_2^{Cu} for the mono- and bis-biguanide complexes respectively, the corresponding nickel complexes show more or less a single-step decomposition. Moreover, no colour changes have been observed in the case with those of copper (Das Sarma and Ray, *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 347). The decomposition of dibiguanide complexes of both copper and nickel, however, are quite satisfactorily represented in the form of a single-stage process:

where A represents a quadridentate dibiguanide molecule. Further discussion on these apparent one-step formation and dissociation of nickel bis-biguanide, copper dibiguanide and nickel dibiguanide complexes will follow in a subsequent communication.

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